

Clopidogrel sticking issue: a systematic review on factors and formulation assessment

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Abstract

Since the expiry of the originator's patent related to clopidogrel in 2012, generic drugs have been extensively manufactured worldwide. However, numerous operational concerns have started to emerge within many pharmaceutical industries. One major concern commonly reported is the problem of tablet formulations adhering to punches and dies during compression. This defect has directed substantial research efforts toward addressing the issue, ranging from root cause analysis to full implementation of solutions. A systematic review was therefore an essential prerequisite to identify, from the literature, the most critical attributes contributing to this defect in order to achieve sticking-free tableting. Data were extracted from patents and reputed scientific articles. Records were assessed based on scientific knowledge, whereby recommendations for future research were subsequently provided.

Keywords

Clopidogrel, compaction, compression, hygroscopic, sticking

Introduction

The high market demand for clopidogrel as an antiplatelet drug has urged numerous pharmaceutical industries to consider clopidogrel as a strategic product. Since it is formulated as tablets, drug manufacturing necessitates the use of tableting machines for powder compression. However, a major concern arises when clopidogrel powder is subjected to compression. The root cause of this concern is primarily attributed to the intrinsic properties of clopidogrel, which render it prone to sticking and picking issues during powder compression (Mishra et al. 2009; Lei et al. 2015; Kovács et al. 2024).

Moreover, the sticking issue associated with clopidogrel is complex due to the existence of the drug in multiple salts and polymorphic forms (Lorimer and Ng 2010). In addition, the drug is highly sensitive to degradation-driving

factors such as moisture, temperature, excipients, solar exposure, pressure, and acidity (Lestari et al. 2010; Osmanović Omerdić et al. 2022).

Generally, direct physical contact between pharmaceutical blends and the punches and dies of compression machines can lead to problematic sticking. This issue represents one of the major challenges in tablet manufacturing. It has been estimated, for example, that 25% of new chemical entities have exhibited sticking problems (Chattoraj et al. 2018). From a pharmaceutical perspective, this estimate indicates a high prevalence of the problem, which has necessitated extensive research efforts aimed at resolving sticking through improved understanding of drug properties and formulation design.

The root causes of sticking in general have been thoroughly investigated by the science-based community, whereby a summary of these causes is outlined in Fig. 1.

Generally, a single factor or a combination of these factors can contribute to the sticking problem, depending on the types and properties of the drug involved, the types and properties of excipients used in drug formulation, and tool type, configuration, and finishing. Among all these factors outlined in Fig. 1, it is important to emphasize the fact that moisture sorption represents the major factor that causes all detrimental consequences upon powder compression (Koumbogle et al. 2023; Le et al. 2025). On the other hand, attempted remedies to resolve the tablet sticking problem have also been reported in the literature. Reviews on this matter are numerous; nevertheless, a summary of the main considerations undertaken for this issue is outlined in Table 1.

The overwhelming research over the past 15 years has been devoted to resolving clopidogrel's sticking issue through identification of the major factors contributing to stickiness. However, there is no systematic research so far bridging separate pieces of information across numerous scientific reports. For example, aspects of clopidogrel's adherence to die and punch walls related to formulation components, drug polymorphism, drug salts, and processing techniques have been discussed separately. This systematic review thus gives special emphasis to the sticking issue of clopidogrel from multiple perspectives. The objective was aimed at extracting, from the literature, the most influential factors contributing to clopidogrel's sticking issue. Assessments are addressed based on scientific knowledge, understanding, and analysis.

Figure 1. Factors causing sticking in pharmaceutical tablet manufacturing.

Table 1. General considerations on the aspects undertaken to resolve tablet sticking issues during pharmaceutical processing.

Considerations in resolving powder stickiness upon tableting					
Lubricants	Moisture	API	Powder for compression	Compression machine	Tools
Type e.g., metallic salts of fatty acids, fatty acid, fatty acid esters, inorganic materials, and polymers (Li and Wu 2014)	Low moisture content excipients e.g., maize starch is preferred over potato due to lower water content. (Slapnig and Krammer 2024)	Low surface area e.g., a dry coating of APIs with MCC lowers surface area, reduces contact with the punch surface, and consequently reduces sticking. (Capece 2019)	Particle size distribution (% fine and coarse particles) Fine particles have a larger surface area for more cohesive forces to adhere to punches and dies. (Cabiscol et al. 2020)	Compression pressure (Paul et al. 2017)	Coated surfaces Coating of metal surfaces reduces surface energy and static friction and thus mitigates sticking. (Lima et al. 2023)
Concentration e.g.: Mg stearate: 0.25–2% Talc: 1–5% Waxes 1–5% (Li and Wu 2014)	No hygroscopic excipients as possible (Ng et al. 2022)	Low surface energy e.g., a dry coating of ezetimibe with silicon dioxide reduces its surface free energy, accompanied by lowering its adhesion tendency. (Tadauchi et al. 2022)	Impact of pressure Pressure affects powder deformation (plastic/elastic or brittle fracture) based on the nature of the powder blend. (Paul et al. 2017)	Pre-compression and dwell time Pre-compression and dwell time affect sticking either positively	Clean e.g., punch tips are usually cleaned using isopropyl alcohol before compressing tablets. (Paul et al. 2017)
Mode of addition e.g., external, or internal lubrication (Xiang and Sun 2024)	Moisture-controlling excipients e.g., silicon dioxide (Blanco et al. 2021)	Compressibility and compatibility The two parameters are an indication of ductility; the higher the ductility, the lower the sticking propensity. (Paul et al. 2017)	Flowability Most APIs have a bad flow due to their small particle size, resulting in a high tendency to stick to punches and dies. (Tadauchi et al. 2022)	or negatively depending on the deformation mode of the powder blend. (Thomas 2023)	Storage conditions Punches and dies are usually stored after adding a layer of liquid paraffin or food-grade oil on their surfaces.
Interaction with the API (Chowhan and Chi 1986)			Attrition e.g., based on the deformation behavior, dicalcium phosphate is most prone to attrition, followed by mannitol, lactose, and microcrystalline cellulose. (Kulkarni et al. 2023)		

Methods

A myriad of studies have previously been reported on antiplatelet drugs. Since the current choice of interest was clopidogrel, it was found that initial reports relevant to this review date back to 1986 on thienopyridine as an antiplatelet compound. This drug was later modified to become clopidogrel (Caplan 2016). However, the current systematic review, carried out using PRISMA (Haddaway et al. 2022), focused on a specific property of clopidogrel related to its adherence to processing tools in the pharmaceutical industry. Accordingly, reports were filtered for this specific investigation from 1986 to 2025. The main criterion adopted in this search was the use of keywords related to the stickiness or adherence of clopidogrel to punches and dies during powder compression. The search was limited by design to the Scopus, PubMed, and Espacenet databases. The first two are among the most reputable databases covering peer-reviewed articles indexed in Web of Science, MEDLINE, EMBASE, and ScienceDirect. The latter, Espacenet, provides access to millions of freely available patent documents. In fact, the Espacenet patent search provided a strong and reliable source for this systematic review, since most technological practices aimed at overcoming tablet stickiness have been patented. Records were screened based on their relevance to the keywords

addressed earlier in this context. Adopted reports were evaluated and assessed using a science-based approach. A few records were excluded, not only due to their irrelevance to the keywords but also due to their inconsistency with logical, science-based justification. Table 2 illustrates the criteria adopted for selecting and excluding screened work. A flow-chart describing the roadmap of the current systematic review is illustrated in Fig. 2. The latter comprises a summary of statistical records adopted for this review and subsequently screened for analysis and assessment.

Results and discussion

Systematic screening on clopidogrel's sticking problem

From the 256 relevant records selected from published work according to Table 2 and then screened for assessment, four main factors were identified (Fig. 3) to directly or indirectly contribute to clopidogrel's powder adherence to compression tools. Moisture absorption and excipients used in drug formulation represent the dominantly reported factors. To a lesser extent, particle size and shape and deformation behavior were also acknowledged to

Figure 2. PRISMA flow chart diagram.

Table 2. Criteria for selecting or excluding published work from the literature for a systematic review associated with clopidogrel's sticking issue.

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Specific	Compression, compaction, moisture content, or excipient(s) related to drug stickiness or drug stability or drug polymorphism	Not a tablet dosage form (e.g., subcutaneous injection)
	Drug adherence to punches and dies: causes or prevention	Sticking or factors causing sticking is/are not an objective(s)
	Drug salts and polymorphs moisture absorption	Data or results are not sufficient to justify objective(s)
	Drug structure related to moisture absorption	No data/justifications displayed to approve correct polymorph, stability, and/or absence of sticking
	Deformation mechanism of the drug resulting in more exposed surface moieties	
	Size and shape resulting in more exposed surface moieties	
General	Techniques involved for drug processing to mitigate stickiness	
	Moisture absorption	Stability of the drug
	Deformation modes and mechanisms	Dissolution of the drug
	Tablet sticking problem	Data are not from Scopus/PubMed articles or from reputable journals.

contribute to the sticking problem. It is important to note that Fig. 3 was not constructed based on reports comprising overlapping factors, since each factor was handled separately, as mentioned beforehand. Each factor will be the subject of thorough discussion in the following sections.

Figure 3. % contribution of factors reported in the literature.

Moisture absorption of clopidogrel

Moisture uptake by clopidogrel is attributed to its structure (Fig. 4). The main bioactive constituent of clopidogrel is thienopyridine. Generally, thienopyridines are bicyclic molecules with an electron-excessive thiophene ring of high polarity originating from polar groups comprising the ester carbonyl oxygen and the tertiary amine nitrogen (Maffrand 2012; Masenenia et al. 2012; Remko et al. 2016). The latter polar group is known to be capable of bonding with water molecules via O–H...N hydrogen bonds (Wang et al. 2020), which represents a key mechanism for water absorption (Fig. 5).

Employing the same mechanism of water absorption, the foregoing is further established for various clopidogrel salts and polymorphs. Examples of these salts include hydrogen sulfate, hydrochloride, acetate, benzoate, hydrobromide,

Figure 4. Structure of clopidogrel.

Figure 5. Ester group in clopidogrel.

fumarate, maleate, citrate, mesylate, besylate, camphor sulfonate, and hydrogen sulfate salt (Kim et al. 2007; Zupančič et al. 2010; Tsoumani et al. 2015).

Among all the aforementioned clopidogrel salts, the crystalline bisulfate is the most widely used in scientific research and the pharmaceutical industry. However, despite having six different polymorphs, only forms I and II of clopidogrel bisulfate are suitable for pharmaceutical dosage forms (Khomane et al. 2012). Nevertheless, hygroscopicity has been established for different clopidogrel salts and polymorphs (Stahl and Wermuth 2008; Zupančič et al. 2010; Liu et al. 2022). In this regard, dynamic vapor sorption has been performed, and the results are summarized in Fig. 6. Since this parameter theoretically represents the moisture uptake of each compound, it can be understood that, under normal relative humidity (RH) conditions, clopidogrel besylate and camphor sulfonate salts are not hygroscopic, whereas both the HCl and the HBr salts exhibit negligible hygroscopicity. However, Fig. 6 further indicates that both

Figure 6. % gain in mass for different salts and polymorphs of clopidogrel subjected to 25%, 50%, and 80% RH.

polymorphs I and II are extremely hygroscopic when the powders are subjected to RH conditions above 70%.

Fig. 6 further indicates that clopidogrel bisulfate polymorph II exhibits much lower hygroscopicity than polymorph I. Such a difference is more likely correlated to differences in crystalline configuration, attributed more specifically to differences in charge density distribution between the two polymorphs. In this regard, the crystalline structure of the clopidogrel cation–bisulfate anion pair (CLP^+ and HSO_4^-) for polymorph II is less dense and thus less electrostatic than that of polymorph I. A patented work claims that the crystalline structure is thermodynamically stabilized by hydrogen bonds along the *c* axis, comprising chains of sulfate ions and perpendicularly linked clopidogrel molecules via $NH\cdots O_5$ hydrogen bonds (Liu et al. 2022). Such thermodynamic stability renders reduced surface free energy through the appearance of polymorph II crystals in the form of aggregates. Consequently, the absence of a similar configuration and thus hydrogen bond stability in the same manner for polymorph I is responsible for its higher surface free energy and its appearance in the form of irregular plates (Koradia et al. 2004; Srivastava et al. 2010).

Despite their excessive moisture uptake characteristics, polymorphs I and II are still preferred over clopidogrel salts in drug product manufacturing. The reason for this preference arguably varies according to different justifications, since some research claims that polymorphs I and II have more stable crystal structures than other clopidogrel salts (Zupančič et al. 2010). On the other hand, drugs comprising clopidogrel salts may have serious clinical consequences, especially when therapeutic efficacy is critical (Darius et al. 2009; Tsoumani et al. 2015).

Deformation behavior

The compression behavior of a powder can be correlated with its stickiness at the die and punch walls through its mode of deformation. The foregoing takes place either through plastic, elastic, or brittle-fracture modes (Antikainen and Yliruusi 2003; Ren et al. 2024). Generally, brittle-fracture compression behavior results in the fragmentation of particles into smaller pieces, whereby the overall exposed surface area becomes larger than that of the original particles before compression. Accordingly, there will be an increased number of moisture-binding groups available for sticking to the metal surfaces of compression tools (O'Donoghue et al. 2019; Takeuchi et al. 2020). Nevertheless, plastic deformation also generates freshly exposed surfaces upon deformation (Al-Hmoud et al. 2020); however, the foregoing is mainly responsible for enhanced interparticulate bonding (Abu Fara et al. 2020), thus leading to increased tensile strength of the produced compacts.

Mathematical compression models are usually used to describe the compression behavior of powders. The Heckel, Kawakita, and Walker equations have been commonly applied, whereby the former is the most widely adopted. In this regard, yield pressure (P_y) has been extensively used to describe whether the material or mixture deforms in plastic or elastic modes or in brittle-fracture modes. More specifically, the higher the P_y value of a material subjected to compression, the greater its tendency toward brittle fracture and the lower its plastic deformation behavior (Govedarica et al. 2012; Rashid et al. 2022).

For clopidogrel powders, there are no data so far describing the compression behavior of most clopidogrel salts, except for the bisulfate salt. In fact, compression

analysis of this salt has been carried out only for polymorphs I and II. Nevertheless, these two polymorphs are widely available in the market due to the accepted stability and bioavailability data they provide.

Data were collected from the literature, rearranged, and plotted in Fig. 7 for yield pressure versus compression force (Khomane et al. 2012). The figure indicates that the yield pressure of clopidogrel bisulfate polymorph I is higher than that of polymorph II. Consequently, polymorph I exhibits higher resistance to plastic deformation than polymorph II. In other words, polymorph I shows a higher tendency to deform by brittle fracture, whereas plastic deformation is more likely to be the dominant mode of deformation for polymorph II. This finding was further confirmed by Khomane et al. (2012), who investigated the compression behavior of compacted clopidogrel bisulfate powders of polymorphs I and II. Rearranged data from their findings were plotted in Fig. 8. Once again, the yield pressures of polymorph I were higher than those of polymorph II, thus suggesting brittle-fracture fragmentation for polymorph I, while plastic deformation is the dominant behavior of polymorph II.

The overall conclusive remark from the latter data on roller-compacted powders is that the intrinsic brittle-fracture nature of polymorph I makes it more susceptible to exposing fresh surfaces for adhesion to die and punch walls than polymorph II. The latter undergoes plastic deformation upon compression, which favors greater interparticulate bridging than the former. This explains the fact that the tensile strength of compacts produced from polymorph II is higher than that of polymorph I (Khomane et al. 2012).

Further work needs to be extensively carried out to achieve a better understanding of the compression behavior of clopidogrel polymorphs, especially since contradicting findings were reported by Yin et al. (2016). They investigated the in situ three-dimensional deformation of the

two polymorphs (I and II) of clopidogrel bisulfate using synchrotron radiation X-ray computed microtomography technology. In this manner, they were able to visualize and quantify the morphology of crystalline particles before and after compression (Yin et al. 2016). However, their findings largely focused on the observation that crystals of polymorph II undergo fragmentation into smaller pieces, whereas those of polymorph I undergo flattening when both are subjected to compression. They attributed this behavior to the brittle-fracture nature of polymorph II, whereas polymorph I was suggested to undergo plastic deformation. Such contrasting findings require reevaluation based on data reproducibility and method validation when synchrotron radiation X-ray computed microtomography technology is employed.

Particle size and shape

It should be emphasized that particle size can play a major role in minimizing the adhesion of clopidogrel bisulfate powder (polymorph I) to compression walls. The findings presented in Fig. 7 highlight the fact that reducing clopidogrel particle size contributes to a decrease in yield pressure values. Thus, increased plastic deformation can be promoted when clopidogrel bisulfate particles are reduced in size. Consequently, lowering the particle size of polymorph I is suggested to strengthen interparticulate bridging due to plastic deformation, presumably at the expense of die wall adherence. However, it has been reported that particle size reduction to 30 μm or smaller enhances surface electrostatic charges and increases moisture absorption tendency (Cho et al. 2014). Accordingly, in the context of die wall adherence, the effect of particle size reduction on increasing moisture absorption predominantly counteracts the effect of reduced yield pressure or increased plastic deformation tendency.

Figure 7. Yield pressure of clopidogrel bisulfate for polymorphs I and II calculated using the Heckel equation for one particle size distribution (D50–D90) for polymorph I and two particle size distributions (D50–D90) for polymorph II.

Figure 8. Yield pressure of compacted granules of clopidogrel bisulfate for polymorphs I and II calculated using the Heckel equation.

With regard to particle shape, clopidogrel bisulfate polymorphs I and II are irregular and rectangular in shape (Yin et al. 2016; An et al. 2019). From the earlier discussion in this report, it has been established that crystals of polymorph I exhibit irregular plate-like structures with high surface free energy. Accordingly, emphasis has been placed on modifying the crystal shape of polymorph I to render a more thermodynamically stable form with reduced susceptibility to hydrogen bonding, such as hygroscopicity resulting in powder stickiness.

In general, particles with more regular surfaces or more spherical shapes are less prone to adhering to tool walls during compression (Shah et al. 2023). Accordingly, several attempts have been made to manufacture polymorph I in spherical particle forms (Chen et al. 2018; An et al. 2019; Liu et al. 2021). However, the main objective of such manufacturing approaches was to produce clopidogrel bisulfate polymorph I agglomerates with higher thermodynamic stability, without conversion to polymorph II, as well as improved solubility and bioavailability compared with those produced using conventional techniques. Table 3 provides a description of several techniques reported in the literature to date.

However, there are no data so far that evaluate processing behavior when powders comprising spherical particles are subjected to compression. Emphasis should be placed in future work on the effect of spherical particles of the two polymorphs with regard to hygroscopicity and stickiness during compression.

Formulations and excipients

Several attempts have been reported to reduce die wall stickiness through formulation of clopidogrel salts with various pharmaceutical excipients. Some of these attempts are summarized in Table 4. Generally, the most common excipient used in the pharmaceutical industry to reduce die-wall friction is magnesium stearate. However, this excipient is not used in either the originator product, Plavix™ by Sanofi-Aventis Company Limited, or in other generic formulations. This has been attributed to interactions between clopidogrel bisulfate and magnesium stearate, which accelerate the formation of undesired degradation products (Sherman 2005). This explains why the lubricants used in Plavix™ are limited to hydrogenated castor oil and

Table 3. Spherical crystallization techniques.

Method	Reference
Spherical crystallization of clopidogrel polymorph I using a mixture of isopropyl alcohol and <i>n</i> -hexane as an antisolvent. This was controlled in terms of temperature, solvents, supersaturation level, and stirring speed.	(An et al. 2019)
Supersaturation-dependent spherulitic growth mechanism using binary solvent systems of either 1-propanol or 1-butanol with isopropyl acetate. The key factors affecting the spherulitic growth process are supersaturation, concentration, and temperature.	(Liu et al. 2021)
Spherical crystallization of form I through the addition of camphor sulfonate into dichloromethane. The solution was processed until the obtained clopidogrel alkali was dissolved in 2-butanol. Concentrated sulfuric acid was added for reaction, followed by crystallization. Temperature was controlled prior to filtration and drying.	(Chen et al. 2018)
Spherical crystallization of form II. Clopidogrel alkali was dissolved in acetone. Concentrated sulfuric acid diluted with acetone was added to the solvent. The reaction was conducted under constant temperature and facilitated spontaneous nucleation. The product was obtained via filtration and then dried.	(Chen et al. 2018)

Table 4. Critical excipients used for the formulation of clopidogrel salts.

Excipients	Method
Colloidal silicon dioxide (Chaudhari and Gupte 2017)	Clopidogrel bisulfate was premixed with colloidal silicon dioxide (equivalent to 2.0% of tablet weight), then granulated with other binders and diluents, dried, and blended with additional colloidal silicon dioxide (equivalent to 0.3% of tablet weight).
Zinc stearate, stearic acid, and sodium stearyl fumarate (Sherman 2005)	Clopidogrel bisulfate was processed with fillers and binders prior to the addition of zinc stearate, stearic acid, and sodium stearyl fumarate as lubricants.
Ascorbic acid, citric acid, malic acid, benzoic acid, and tartaric acid (Chowhan 1986)	Ascorbic acid, citric acid, malic acid, benzoic acid, and tartaric acid were used to prevent degradation of the drug.
Hydrogenated vegetable oil (Makhamov et al. 2025)	Clopidogrel bisulfate was processed with hydrogenated vegetable oil, which was used as a lubricant.
Hydrogenated vegetable oil (Ramaswami et al. 2005)	Clopidogrel mesylate, hydroiodide, hydrobromide, and hydrochloride particles were coated with polyvinyl acetate or polyvinyl alcohol in combination with hydrogenated vegetable oil.
A combination of lactose, microcrystalline cellulose, stearic acid, and hydrogenated castor oil (Maffrand 2012)	Clopidogrel hydrobromide or clopidogrel hydrochloride was processed with lactose, microcrystalline cellulose, stearic acid, and hydrogenated castor oil.

polyethylene glycol, despite the fact that magnesium stearate is more effective than both (Zheng et al. 2024). Nevertheless, the former lubricants appear to affect tablet tensile strength to a lesser extent than the latter (Wang et al. 2010).

Hydrogenated castor oil has been further used in a patented work in combination with sodium carboxymethyl starch in clopidogrel bisulfate formulations (Öncel and Erkahraman 2005). This approach was undertaken to improve tableability and reduce problems associated with compression. It has been suggested that the good binding and thickening properties of sodium carboxymethyl starch played a major role in this improvement (Makhamov et al. 2025). Although the same patented work claimed instability between sodium carboxymethyl starch and clopidogrel, the combination of sodium carboxymethyl cellulose and hydrogenated castor oil was reported to provide a stable environment for clopidogrel. Nevertheless, this interaction has not been reported elsewhere in the literature.

Furthermore, hydrogenated castor oil, representing the hydrophobic phase, has been used in another patented work in combination with polyvinyl acetate or polyvinyl alcohol as a coating step for particles, granules, or agglomerates of clopidogrel salt. The salt was selected from mesylate, hydrobromide, hydroiodide, and hydrochloride (Bharatrajan et al. 2005). The purpose of this work was to establish an effective moisture barrier around the particles or tablets. Product stability was confirmed after 1–2 months of incubation at room temperature. However, no stability data were reported for longer periods or under accelerated conditions. In addition, another patented work reported that experiments conducted using the aforementioned excipients resulted in tablets exhibiting sticking problems (Chowhan 1986).

Another patented work remains uncertain regarding the effectiveness of hydrogenated castor oil in eliminating clopidogrel adherence to die walls. Instead, this work adopted the use of zinc stearate, stearic acid, and sodium stearyl fumarate as lubricants most comparable to magnesium stearate (Sherman 2005). With regard to degradation products expressed as a percentage of the initial clopidogrel bisulfate content, the patented work included

a stability investigation conducted at 60 °C for a period of 2 weeks. The results confirmed stability under these conditions. However, a comprehensive stability study that considers official temperature ranges, humidity conditions, and appropriate durations should be conducted to confirm drug stability for regulatory approval.

On the other hand, other attempts have not excluded the use of magnesium stearate as a lubricant; however, stability was maintained over the shelf life of the formulation. In this regard, antioxidant additives comprising ascorbic acid and citric acid, as well as malic acid and tartaric acid, have been used as stabilizers. These additives were recommended as being added to prevent degradation (Chowhan 1986). However, the aforementioned work was performed on thienopyridine drugs. Since both clopidogrel and thienopyridine are thienopyridine antiplatelet drugs that are structurally related (Maffrand 2012), it is expected that the behavior of the two drugs is similar. Once again, there is strong emphasis on conducting stability analysis on clopidogrel using the aforementioned stabilizers for future regulatory approval.

One interesting patented work tested the effect of single excipients and combinations of excipients on the stickiness of clopidogrel tablets. The clopidogrel salt used for testing was hydrobromide. In this work, clopidogrel stickiness was greatly influenced by combinations of excipients mixed with combinations of lubricants. Some excipients or their combinations had no contribution to reducing the extent of drug adherence to die walls. In contrast, other excipients eliminated this problematic issue, even under direct compression tableting conditions. Table 5 summarizes the findings related to the contribution of individual excipients and their combinations to the extent of stickiness. Based on Table 5, the patented work concluded that mixtures of lactose and mannitol, lubricated with mixtures of stearic acid and hydrogenated castor oil, resulted in formulations free of sticking (Maffrand 2012).

On the other hand, it is important to consider the fact that the grade of mannitol has a significant impact on the sticking problem. In this regard, powdered mannitol exhibits higher sticking intensity compared with granular mannitol (Gahoi et al. 2008).

Table 5. Excipients and their combinations versus the extent of sticking during compression (high or low) (Gahoi et al. 2008).

Excipient/mixture of excipients	Extent of sticking (high, low)
Mannitol	High
Mannitol + microcrystalline cellulose	High
Mannitol + lactose	High
Lactose	Low
Lactose + microcrystalline cellulose	Low
Glyceryl behenate	High
Polyethylene glycol	High
Hydrogenated castor oil	High
Hydrogenated castor oil + polyethylene glycol	High
Stearic acid + hydrogenated castor oil	Low

Since the choice of excipient is critical in reducing die wall adherence, a patented work pursued a similar objective using a different excipient (Chaudhari and Gupte 2017). In this work, colloidal silicon dioxide was adopted as an antiadherent and coating agent for the purpose of providing complete isolation of the clopidogrel bisulfate surface. Such isolation is generally attributed to coverage of the drug surface, thus reducing its sticking tendency to metal surfaces. It should be noted that, theoretically, colloidal silicon dioxide functions as a good insulator with very high electrical resistance, which is capable of charging surfaces and controlling the spacing between adjacent particles (Lei et al. 2015).

The method adopted in this patented work was as follows: clopidogrel bisulfate was mixed with colloidal silicon dioxide. A diluent was added to the mixture, followed by granulation with a binder solution. The wet granules were dried, milled, and blended with a disintegrant, a lubricant, and a glidant, namely colloidal silicon dioxide. However, the total content of colloidal silicon dioxide in the tablet was reported to be 2.75%. Generally, this glidant is used at up to 1% of the total tablet content. Higher levels may adversely affect the mechanical strength of the tablets produced (Anderson 1999).

Using a different pathway involving advanced instrumentation, another patented work reported a reduction in clopidogrel sticking through encapsulation by spray drying (Mishra et al. 2009). In this work, clopidogrel base was dissolved with butylated hydroxyanisole in isopropanol. The solution was mixed with a blend of mannitol, lactose anhydrous, microcrystalline cellulose, colloidal silicon dioxide, and sucrose. The resulting suspension was spray-dried and then further processed to obtain the desired formulation.

Although the aforementioned technique demonstrated drug stability at 40 °C and 75% RH for a period of 6 months, processing using organic solvents is not favorable in most industrial procedures. Alternatively, Kim et al. (2007) reported spray drying a clopidogrel salt using water as the solvent. In this regard, they developed a solid dispersion system of clopidogrel napadisilate monohydrate suitable for spray drying, using Tween 80 as a surfactant

and hydroxypropyl methylcellulose as a binder. The resulting powder showed improved stability, enhanced oral bioavailability, and, most importantly, no sticking problems (Hentzschel et al. 2012). Interestingly, the same spray-dried clopidogrel napadisilate monohydrate product was later investigated using roller compaction in a separate study.

The work on roller compaction, as discussed earlier in this report, was confined to highlighting deformation differences between clopidogrel bisulfate polymorphs I and II. However, to the authors' knowledge, no feasibility data were reported on the use of roller compaction for achieving improved powder processing and tableability. Recently, a quality by design (QbD) approach has been implemented to optimize the manufacturing process of clopidogrel tablets via dry granulation (Bak et al. 2025). This approach was selected to mitigate degradation risks associated with solvents used in conventional wet granulation. The experimental design of this work is illustrated in the schematic diagram presented in Fig. 9.

Figure 9. A schematic diagram representing processing of a clopidogrel napadisilate preparation from mixing through roll compaction and ending with powder compression.

The interesting finding in the aforementioned work is that no tableting defects—including sticking and capping—were recorded during compression. The same work further noted that this finding was confirmed for a lubrication period of 3–5 minutes. However, an investigation into the deformation behavior of clopidogrel napadisilate would provide a clearer picture of the yield pressure range or fragmentation extent as a function of applied pressure. This would define the limits of operating pressure for compaction without the possible occurrence of powder sticking problems.

Conclusion

The current systematic review was performed in alignment with the industrial necessity to resolve the sticking issue of clopidogrel. In the records screened in patents and highly reputed scientific articles, four factors were identified as the dominant attributes contributing to the sticking issue. Moisture absorption and excipients used in drug formulations were the most frequently reported attributes, whereas particle size and shape and deformation behavior were also reported, but to a lesser extent. Corrective actions established to mitigate clopidogrel adherence to die and punch walls during compression were assessed and found to strictly consider a combination of additional factors, including the type of clopidogrel salt, type of polymorph, preparation method (wet or dry granulation), compression and compaction pressure, particle size and surface morphology, and type of excipients present. Despite the reported achievements in establishing reduced-sticking or stick-free tablets, there remains a need for further evidence to be presented in the context of producing a product of acceptable quality.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The author declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The author declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The author declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The author declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The author declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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